

Rabi Frequency and Optimization of Transfer of Information?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 3, 2023

In (1) a model of information transfer via a “coin” with probabilities p and $1-p$ is used together with a binomial distribution to show that $\sin(\text{information})\sin(\text{information})$ is the probability distribution which maximizes the binomial distribution. (1) suggests that the $\sin(\text{information})\sin(\text{information})$ probability may be applicable to describing polarizations. In (2), we argued that the form $\sin(\text{information})\sin(\text{information})$ is part of the probability linked with $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = \cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px)$, with information px . (1) also notes that $\sin(\text{information})\sin(\text{information})$ is a probability associated with a real function and not the complex valued wavefunction.)

Given that we apply $\sin(px)\sin(px)$ to $\exp(ipx)$, a similar result should hold for $\exp(-iEt)$. The periodic form of $\exp(-iEt)$, however, is key in the Rabi result of the state $\exp(-iE_0 t) |0\rangle + \exp(-iE_1 t) |1\rangle$ oscillating in time, up to a time phase. The Rabi result leads to a probability $\langle W | B \rangle \langle B | W \rangle$ at t proportional to $\sin((E_1 - E_0)/2 t) \sin((E_1 - E_0)/2 t)$ i.e. the result of (1) with .5 multiplied by a photon frequency $E_1 - E_0$ i.e. the photon which excites the system from E_0 to E_1 . Here $|B\rangle = \exp(i\phi) \{ a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle \}$ and $|W \text{ at } t\rangle = a \exp(-iE_0 t) |0\rangle + b \exp(-iE_1 t) |1\rangle$ with $a^2 + b^2 = 1$.

In other words the information is $w/2$ where w is the photon frequency. In the case of a photon, however, the idea of a binomial distribution becomes clear because one has a state $|0\rangle$ without a photon and a state $|1\rangle$ with one and the overall wavefunction is a sum of the two. In other words a binomial distribution fits this picture in addition to being associated with px and Et from $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, we argue.

Maximum Transfer of Information

The model of (1) describes a person A who has information about a variable X in the range $(0$ to $3.14/2)$ and sends information about X encoded in a probability p to a second person B. This probability p is linked with obtaining heads in a coin toss (p for heads, $1-p$ for tails). Probability p means the coin is heads and this represents useful information regarding the variable according to some prescription. Thus, person B wishes to find the probability p and must perform a number of test runs. A binomial distribution is used (using p and $1-p$) with the number of trial runs N approaching infinite. In this limit, (1) links weights created using probability p to the fraction:

$$\{ \text{0 to information value} \} / \{ \text{0 to } 3.14/2 \} \quad ((1))$$

As a result, (1) finds that the maximum information transfer is associated with a probability of:

$$\sin(\text{information})\sin(\text{information}) \quad ((2))$$

(1) associates this probability with polarization, but in (2) we argued that this is also found in $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ with px being the information.

In such a case, one may also extend this idea to include $\exp(-iEt)\exp(iEt)$. In other words the $\sin(\cdot)\sin(\cdot) + \cos(\cdot)\cos(\cdot)$ form of a rotating vector is linked with maximization of information transfer.

Rabi Frequency

The periodicity of $\exp(-iEt)$ has important consequences for a two level system with ground state energy E_0 and excited state E_1 with E_1-E_0 representing the energy of a photon. In general, one may write the two level system as:

$$|W \text{ at } t\rangle = a\exp(-i E_0 t) |0\rangle + b\exp(-i E_1 t) |1\rangle \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{where } aa+bb=1 \quad ((4))$$

One may immediately see that due to the periodicity of the form $\exp(-i Et)$, $|W \text{ t}=0\rangle$ becomes $\exp(-i E_0 t) |W \text{ t}=0\rangle$ if $t = 2\pi / (E_1-E_0)$.

In (3), the term of interest is defined in a different manner. At $t=0$, one has:

$$|W \text{ t}=0\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle \quad ((5a)) \text{ An orthonormal second wavefunction is:}$$

$$|B\rangle = \exp(i\phi) \{ a|0\rangle - b|1\rangle \} \quad ((5b))$$

(3) is concerned with: $\langle W \text{ at } t | B \rangle \langle B | W \text{ at } t \rangle$ which may be shown to be proportional to:

$$\{ 2 - 2 \cos((E_1-E_0)t) \} \quad ((6)) \quad (\hbar=1)$$

$$((6)) \text{ in turn is proportional to: } \sin((E_1-E_0) t / 2) \sin((E_1-E_0) t / 2) \quad ((7))$$

In other words, if $W \text{ at } t=0$ becomes $\exp(-i E_0 t_1) |W \text{ at } t=0\rangle$ for some time t_1 , then ((7)) should become 0. This means that: $t = 2/(E_1-E_0)$ i.e. the time at half the time wavelength of the photon.

Link with Information

The approach of (1) is to consider a binomial probability. We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ both are associated with $\sin(px)\sin(px)$ or $\sin(Et)\sin(Et)$, but ((7)) is associated with $\sin(\cdot)\sin(\cdot)$ of a different piece of information, namely half the frequency of the photon $(E_1-E_0)/2$ because one only needs $\sin(3.14)=0$. In this case, both $|W \text{ t}=0\rangle$ and $|B\rangle$ are combinations of states with and without a photon and so seem to give rise conceptually to the idea of a binomial distribution which may be used with $N \rightarrow$ infinite trials and optimized.

We suggest that through $\exp(-iEt)$, the Rabi probability $\langle W \text{ at } t | B \rangle \langle B | W \text{ at } t \rangle$ is also of the form of $\sin((E_1-E_0)t / 2) \sin((E_1-E_0)t / 2)$. We suggest this may be another example of the result of (1).

Conclusion

In (1), it is suggested that information about a variable X distributed on $(0, \pi/2)$ and known by person A may be “somehow” encoded into the probability p of heads for a coin given to person B. Person B must find the probability p in order to learn about the value of X . Person B performs a number of trial runs ($N \rightarrow \infty$) and optimizes a binomial distribution. It is shown in (1) that the optimized probability p is of the form: $\sin(\text{information})$. (1) argues that this result might apply to polarization.

In (2) we argue that $\sin(px)\cos(px)$ is associated with $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ i.e. px is the information. Here we extend this to $\exp(-iEt)$. The form $\exp(-iEt)$, however, is key to obtaining the Rabi oscillation result. One considers a two level system E_0, E_1 with the wavefunction $|W$ at $t\rangle = a \exp(-iE_0 t) |0\rangle + b \exp(-iE_1 t) |1\rangle$ where $a^2 + b^2 = 1$. At $t=0$, one has $|W t=0\rangle = a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle$. An orthonormal vector to this is: $|B\rangle = \exp(i\phi) \{ a|0\rangle - b|1\rangle \}$. In (3) the probability of interest is: $\langle W$ at $t|B\rangle \langle B|W$ at $t\rangle$ which may be shown to be proportional to $\sin((E_1 - E_0)t/2) \cos((E_1 - E_0)t/2)$. This probability is 0 when \sin has an argument of $\pi/2$ which is half of the photon frequency. We argue that the $\sin(\cdot)\cos(\cdot)$ form may be another example of the result of (1). In this case, the wavefunction is a combination of one with a photon and without although it is again the cycling feature which is related to the oscillation of probability.

References

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